

Interview with Character Designer Ai Yokoyama at FicZone 2025

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CoolJapan.es

Illustration of Bayonetta by Ai Yokoyama

Ai Yokoyama — 山口県, Yamaguchi Prefecture, Japan — is an illustrator and character designer who has worked on numerous projects for the Gonzo studio. A fan of the franchise, she was responsible for designing the main characters for *Bayonetta: Bloody Fate*, adapting Mari Shimazaki's original game designs for the animated version under her supervision. She also contributed to the team behind *Basilisk*, a series well known in the West.

She joined Madhouse in 2007 and currently works as a freelancer. In addition to *Bloody Fate*, she has designed characters for other animation projects such as *Usukozakura – GARO the Movie*, TV series including *X-MEN* and *Space Battleship Tiramisu*, and has provided illustrations for CD covers for artists like Aoi Eir and Kalafina. During her time at Madhouse, she met artist and director Naomi Nakayama, with whom she maintains a strong professional relationship and whom we also interviewed at FicZone 2025.

Highly versatile, her style blends elegance, fluidity, and faithfulness to the original sources, as successfully demonstrated in the refreshed yet recognisable aesthetic of *Bayonetta: Bloody Fate*.

If you enjoy any of the artworks featured in this entry, you can purchase originals via her website. She also regularly shares new works on social media and announces when she is available for commissions, discounts, or promotions.

Interview with Ai Yokoyama

Cool Japan: You began your career at Madhouse and now work freelance. How has your way of working changed over time?

Ai Yokoyama: That's right, it has changed. Madhouse, for example, has a very defined style. I specialise in shōnen, and since then I'm grateful to receive more jobs with realistic images and styles, which is what I'm good at. I can choose the work I want.

CJ: You designed characters for *Bayonetta: Bloody Fate*. How do you approach creating such strong and stylised characters? You've also worked on projects where the characters belong to other authors, such as *Attack on Titan*. How is that experience for you?

AY: The initial design is very simple. But since the characters have to move, I gradually modify them during the animation of the scenes. I add emotions and details according to the scene. The level of detail increases with the scene.

Regarding *Shingeki*, I only participated as an assistant, I didn't have a directing role, so I didn't have much influence.

CJ: What is your preferred technique and medium for creating artwork?

AY: I think there are many ways to draw and design, but my favourite is analogue painting. Today I'm going to paint a large piece on the wall where I'll be performing, it will be shown live!

I also use my iPad for daily work. It's very convenient and has many apps to practise with.

CJ: You've collaborated with artists like Eir Aoi and Kalafina on covers and illustrations. How do you approach directing an animated sequence with music?

AY: My main work is drawing, a character, faces... Directing an entire sequence is fun and rewarding. When working on a sequence that includes music, you have to think about the whole; it's a completely different approach.

CJ: Are there any artists or creators who have particularly influenced your style? I think animation from the 90s and early 2000s is some of the best in anime history.

AY: Yes, there's one work that influenced me greatly: Madhouse's *Vampire Hunter D: Bloodlust*, directed by Yoshiaki Kawajiri. I wanted to work at Madhouse to be close to the people responsible. And I agree with you [referring to the animation from the 90s and 2000s being exceptional].

CJ: Is there any project or series you remember fondly or that was a turning point for you?

AY: [Laughs] *Arslan Senki* [*The Heroic Legend of Arslan*, 2015], the endings I created together with Nakayama-san [referring to Naomi Nakayama, also present at FicZone 2025], were something we enjoyed because we had a lot of creative freedom. Since we were free to do those sequences, I worked really well.

CJ: Which anime director would you like to work with, or work with again?

AY: Kawajiri-san [referring to the veteran Yoshiaki Kawajiri, director of *Vampire Hunter D: Bloodlust*].

CJ: What advice would you give to those who want to become character designers in animation?

AY: Nowadays there are more and more talented people from abroad working in Japan, so if you can dedicate yourself to drawing for many hours, you can become an animator.

You have the opportunity!

Ai Yokoyama, on the left, in front of a mural she created for the series *Basilisk* to commemorate its 20th anniversary, during Anime Expo 2025.

Acknowledgements

We cannot say goodbye without thanking Ai Yokoyama herself. Beyond her talent as an artist, she stood out for her good humour, great character, and genuine enthusiasm for the projects she has participated in.

She even brought a small Bayonetta soft toy—very similar to the chibi version from the games. She truly enjoyed the interview, and we were able to see her draw in person during the event, creating numerous signatures and illustrations for attendees.

Once again, we also thank the FicZone team and the CrossOver association for their excellent support; the event's press team and volunteers; and, of course, Michie Yamaya, tireless and cheerful interpreter, without whom, once again, this interview would not have been possible.

Additionally, Yokoyama recorded a greeting for the followers of CoolJapan.es, available on YouTube via the following link!

Sources

- **Texts consulted from:** KoukyouZen, Anime News Network, Official FicZone website | **Interview conducted by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es] | **Interview interpreted by:** Michie Yamaya
- **Images sourced from:** Official Ai Yokoyama website, Official X account of Ai Yokoyama

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